

Value Co-Creation and the Collaboration; the Precise Factors Needed to Sustain in the Educational Industry at Times of Adversity

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ABSTRACT

This writing presents the ideas for creating value co-creation of existing operations of the institution and utilizing it extensively. After, a dramatic effect caused by the adversity, students and educators have already adapted actively to the change and accepted the respective participatory roles that allow them to be interactive to the management and the students (through the virtual medium). Value co-creation is the process in which value is created through equal collaboration and widely utilizing institutional resources at its best. The writing can be used to help inform and may guide practice for the faculty and administration within to broaden the foundations. Moreover, to re-revise their practices and build new bendable alternatives either by new business strategy or doing new negotiation deals to maintain the balance of the existing operations of the institution.

INTRODUCTION

Educational industry is an industry whose main objective is to provide education that encompasses from schools, colleges, universities to ministries of education; which eventually leads to the competitive advantage to the global economy and the whole educational system. Additionally, adversity is the term derived from the circumstances or stroke of unpleasant situation such as COVID-19. In relevance to the research topic, at the present moment, the world is facing a new challenge against biological welfare which is pretty much changing the dynamics of the educational industry drastically. However, value co-creation and collaboration are the two main precise factors that can be combined to help in maintenance and engagement of the educational industry.

Furthermore, the factors can tackle to manage the complexity of each department within the organization by actively collaborating with the internal and external divisions and their subdivisions. To be more simple, as the motive denotes "the power of teamwork is proven in times of crisis" which further can help build much better flexible options to help the operations of the educational industry running at an overlooked pace.

The purpose of this study is to provide detailing of the outlook mentioned with the trends that are occurring concerning the global backlash. Moreover, the document uses exploratory-secondary research by using qualitative method.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In this research body, the subject is examined through providing relevant information experienced in past through organizations and linking with the current time to enhance the development to sustain in the educational institution. Four articles were reviewed and are discussed below.

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Rethinking business education for relevance in business and society in times of disruptive change

This is an exploratory study that tries to answer the research question “What needs for changes in business education curricula are expressed by leading international corporations in the face of disruptive change towards a circular economy?” It’s similar to this research as it too focuses on the inevitable change to our learning mechanisms inevitably caused by disruptive change or adversary. The study expresses the need for integrated systems knowledge, ecosystem design and collaborative innovation efforts. The focus of this research is to highlight the lack of curricular material that focuses on the efforts to reduce global warming per the United Nations climate change conference held in Paris in 2015. The study further talks about the need for a generation of leaders in sustainability. The core of this study is focused on Business schools and the necessity of additional research on the importance of negotiations and their impact on sustainability.

RESEARCH

Purpose of the research

This research aims to determine the value co-creation and collaboration are the two key elements needed for growth to sustain in the educational industry. Also, releasing these elements can further enhance all core operations of the educational industry.

Methods of research

In this study, the method of research applied is exploratory-secondary research where the platforms utilized are online, reviewing the literature and case studies from the body of knowledge. Moreover, the study is exploratory since it aims to determine the hardships of the current situation and exploring through collecting data, attending virtual webinars, and observing the day-to-day reliable news updates through the virtual medium.

Webinar

In this exploratory study, the webinar was attended on Apr 14, 2020, 12:00 PM, Dubai, UAE through the virtual medium which is Zoom. This webinar was conducted for educational industries especially schools to help provide relevant information and innovative ideas to help sustain the value of knowledge transfer.

Precisely, there is a deep clear link of this study underlining the bendable alternatives with the webinar attended which indistinctly mentions by the terms collaboration and engagement during remote learning for the Finnish Education. In the first session, the information provided was about collaboration and engagement of K12 students from home and how schools and homes in both the UAE and Finland have been managing in recent weeks. The format was interactive and practical in providing bendable alternatives to the educational industry at times of adversity (COVID-19).

The session was hosted by Jaakko Skantsi, Counsellor of Education and Science at Embassy of Finland in Abu Dhabi, Philippa Wraithmell, Director of Digital Technology and Innovation at Cranleigh Abu Dhabi and Katia Al-Kaisi, Founder and CEO of Education House Finland. Additionally, the main agenda of this webinar was to provide reflections from Finland and UAE by Counsellor of Education and Science at the Embassy of Finland.

Data Collection

The reliable information obtained from attending this webinar is how in distance learning with the use of extensive technology helped keep the flow of the educational industry. Moreover, creating a virtual replica of the real day-to-day activities as needed in all educational industry. Before shut down or lockdown, the webinar helped in clearing a most common question that schools, colleges and universities do not need those fancy readymade scriptures to engage. Although, a main key element can be by keeping the flow direct, simple and comprehensive in an adjustable manner to help diminish confusion between the educators and students concerning their levels. Furthermore, this can be achieved by two-way communication between teachers and students with effective collaboration

method with the use of technology in remote working style.

The global situation has hit faster than anyone would have imagined. Its effects on schools and universities closures require the rapid need for distance learning solutions.

For instance, the tools that can support distance learning are as follows:-

- EDUTEN
- SEPPPO
- GRAPHOGAME
- HY+ CENTRE FOR CONTINUING EDUCATION
- QRIDI
- KIDE SCIENCE
- MEHACKIT
- SANAKO++
- FREED TEACHERS
- FUN ACADEMY
- EMATHSTUDIO

Statistical question

To add statistical relevance to the study a teacher collaboration question was asked during the live webinar.

Question. Do you work with other teachers to build a more coherent learning experience for the students? (E.g. utilizing the same learning materials across different discipline/subjects?)

- No, I haven't got time for that
- No, the curriculum does not allow that
- Yes, I work with 1-2 different teachers across subject boundaries
- Yes, I work with 3 or more different teachers across subject boundaries

Table 1. Poll results of estimated 30 audiences in size

Statistical Results	
Answers	Results in percentage
No, I haven't got time for that	3%
No, the curriculum does not allow that	11%
Yes, I work with 1-2 different teachers across subject boundaries	50%
Yes, I work with 3 or more different teachers across subject boundaries	37%

Observation's

The Theory Observation:

The relevance of this webinar attended validates this study by providing alternative solutions which are quite bendable and easy to grasp which are as follows by three main pointers which are;

- Peer review
- Quality peer collaboration guidelines
- Peer assessment

Specifically, from this event, the observation conducted addresses options in the form of factors which benefits the study of value co-creation and collaboration needed to sustain in the educational industry when adversity prevails. Firstly, according to the panellist, educational industries must help in minimizing the fear factor by overlooking the pace as it used to be during the normal times because the risk is very high of quality to crumble. Secondly, minimizing the confusion caused by the pandemic and creating much better flexible boundaries such as one-to-one parents and educator's sessions,

providing clear guidelines, and easy catered application which can be accessible through domestic devices. Thirdly, providing effective easy-to-go solutions with the help of upgradable solutions to enhance the technology with guided manuals. Lastly, all the above factors can further enhance and provide a safe environment which can keep the educational industry ideology of educating and transferring valuable knowledge intact for all educational government, entities and institutions of the UAE for reaching out the goal for expo 2020.

The Statistical Observation:

According to table 1: The results show 50% of people agreed on teacher collaboration is more effective when worked with different teachers across subject boundaries. This perhaps signifies the importance of the study that collaboration in any form of action is effective and creates value that enhances the coherent learning experience of the students in the fields of education at the times of uncertainty.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study highlights the various variables involved in the education industry which can be looked into for the co-creation of value through collaborative efforts. The current climate is a very vivid example of the importance of this study. In a globalized effort tackling the adversary of Covid-19, it has been a fundamental shift in the process of routine education. The shift towards online education is not without its challenges. And the questions answered in this exploratory study bring out the importance of collaboration especially as seen in the statistical analysis that shows that a clear majority of educators believe in the need for a more collaborative effort that is not limited by subjective boundaries. The study is both a reflection of education in adversity whilst also being an instruction manual. However, this study is still one of the few works done on this subject. Deeper more analytic research over larger sample groups is still needed to better understand this shift from traditional education to the online approach. The validity and the importance of this study are both seen in the current situation and the lack of material thereof. To future researchers, one of the key recommendations would be to have a higher sample group and to have a control group to see the difference in the two environments and the creation of value. That would also lead to a higher understanding of the creation of and perception of value.

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